

**RECENT CHANGES IN LEGISLATION IN THE FIELD OF LABOR
MIGRATION IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6528587>

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Abstract. *This thesis examines the recent significant changes in the field of labor migration of the Republic of Uzbekistan and bilateral agreements with States hosting a large number of Uzbek labor migrants. Also, the thesis examines Uzbekistan's efforts to create jobs and promote employment within the country, especially among young people. Based on the analysis done, proposals and recommendations on existing problems are put forward.*

Keywords: *migration, labor migration, cooperation, agreement, human rights, labor.*

Последние изменения в законодательстве в области трудовой миграции в Республике Узбекистан

АННОТАЦИЯ: *В этом тезисе рассматриваются последние значительные изменения в области трудовой миграции Республики Узбекистан и двусторонние соглашения с государствами, принимающими большое количество узбекских трудовых мигрантов. Также, в тезисе рассмотрены усилия Узбекистана по созданию рабочих мест и содействию занятости внутри страны, особенно среди молодежи. На основе проделанного анализа выдвигаются предложения и рекомендации по существующим проблемам.*

Ключевые слова: *миграция, трудовая миграция, сотрудничество, соглашение, права человека, труд.*

Widely recognized as an important factor in economic development, the labor world grace has become a priority on the national agenda in recent years. The current government is taking big steps to legalize the organization bathing labor migration and directs the available national assets to activities activity that contributes to socio-economic development within the country. Labor migration with the right organization leads to an increase in employment and family income, an increase in the number of the quality of a skilled workforce and reduce pressure on the labor market and social tension. During this period, many qualities were

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

adopted essentially new legal instruments that are expected to help regulate and alleviate the hardships faced by Uzbek migrants working or planning to work abroad. The new measures are also aimed at covering reducing travel costs and facilitating migrants obtaining permits, insurance, pensions or loans, as well as ensuring the protection of the labor rights of migrants after their departure.

Today, the issue of ensuring the safety of migrant workers is one of the priority tasks facing the States of the world. Because due to the constantly growing population of the Earth, labor migration is increasing every day, including the demand for labor. Migration promotes the exchange of work skills and experience, promotes personal development and affects the size and shape of families and the structure of the population [1].

In recent years, Uzbekistan has been making significant efforts to reregulation of organized labor migration. The country has entered into a series far-reaching agreements with states hosting large the number of Uzbek labor migrants, thereby supporting the labor completion of own citizens abroad. Important attention is also given to efforts to create jobs and promote employment within the country, especially among young people, and 2021 was announced by the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "Year of youth support and strengthening public health". Meanwhile, the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic negatively affected the national labor force, including returnees migrants, and forced the Government of Uzbekistan to adopt additional effective measures to ensure legal and social protection of labor migrants to mitigate these negative impacts.

Labor migration of the Uzbek population is not a new phenomenon. Previous The government tried, albeit inactively, to regulate labor migration in order to promote effects of the socio-economic development of the country. However, there are some factors hindering the regulation and improvement of labor migration, especially insufficient legal base, the existing bureaucratic obstacles and the lack of bilateral and multi-international labor migration agreements with other countries hindered all efforts to combat irregular labor migration. new government, on the contrary, recognized the problems of migration and the various difficulties faced by Uzbek labor migrants, and is playing an increasingly active role in supporting labor migrants.

The starting point for comprehensive reforms in Uzbekistan was the adoption of the Strategy actions in five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, providing for: (i) improving the state and public construction; (ii) ensuring the rule of law, further reforming the judicial system; (iii) economic development and liberalization; (iv) social sphere development; (v)

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, as well as implementing a balanced, mutually beneficial and constructive foreign policy. It is important to note that the fourth direction of this Strategy provides for the implementation of specific measures aimed at increasing employment of the population, improving the system of social protection and protecting the health of citizens [2].

To implement the objectives of the Strategy in the field of social protection, the Ministry of Labor was transformed into the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, which was entrusted with the introduction of new approaches to the implementation of state policy in the field of employment and development of labor market infrastructure [3]. At the same time, the Ministry established the Agency for External Labor Migration, which was entrusted with assisting actions to citizens of Uzbekistan in the implementation of their right to work for abroad. This is achieved through effective management and monitoring of processes organized recruitment, as well as the preparation and implementation of measures for adaptation and labor device abroad. In addition, the Agency is entrusted with the task of interaction with the competent authorities of foreign states in matters of regulation of the process of employment of citizens of Uzbekistan abroad and protection of their labor rights.

The next step of the Government was to allow private employment agencies provide employment services to Uzbek citizens abroad. Regulation of private employment agencies is now enshrined in the Law on private employment agencies, which provides for the increase and expansion of opportunities for workers completion of citizens both at domestic enterprises and abroad [4]. Law establishes a clear regulation of the mechanisms of interaction between public services and the private sector of employment, determining the procedure and conditions provision of employment services, including the rights and obligations of private agencies employment, businesses and individuals, as well as job seekers. This law prohibits private employment agencies collect money from citizens looking for work abroad, stipulating that such payment funded by the employer. According to the law, contracts on the provision of services are recorded in real time in the information labor-migration system of the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations. In order to increasing job security for citizens seeking work abroad, providing for the conclusion of cooperation agreements between private employment agencies and foreign employers or partners, according to which such guarantees will be determined as a necessary prerequisite for employment.

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

Speaking at a meeting of the CIS Council of Heads of State on December 18, 2020, the President Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev proposed the creation within the framework of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS) of a single interstate mechanism for the mutual recognition of documents confirming professional competence and qualification of labor migrants, their medical examination [5]. Proposal of the President on the development and adoption of the Program of Cooperation on labor migration is another important initiative designed to ensure sustainable socio-economic development of the CIS member states.

Uzbekistan actively signs bilateral and intergovernmental agreements with countries hosting a large number of migrant workers, introducing organized forms of cooperation and providing support to citizens of Uzbekistan. One such agreement was signed between the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Government of the Russian Federation to ensure the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of Uzbek migrant workers engaged in temporary labor activity on the territory of the Russian Federation.

In April 2019 The President of the Republic of Kazakhstan paid a state visit to Uzbekistan to sign a bilateral agreement on the protection of the labor rights of citizens of Kazakhstan working in Uzbekistan and the same conditions for citizens of Uzbekistan working in Kazakhstan [6].

As already mentioned, the Government has launched an online database Labor Migration. uz - which contains information about the rules of stay, working conditions, social and housing provision in the country of future employment [7]. It also highlights the legal aspects of concluding employment contracts with foreign employers and financial support measures provided for by law. Registered labor migrants who find themselves in a difficult situation abroad can also use the portal Labor Migration.uz to apply for help to the Labor Migration Agency.

In order to reduce the outflow of human capital that has taken place over the past decades, the key objectives of the national labor migration policy are to provide young people with the opportunity to improve their competence, to enable them to contribute and benefit from an economically viable and legislatively favorable environment, as well as to ensure their full participation as active citizens. A recent event was the signing of the Presidential Decree "On additional measures aimed at attracting entrepreneurship", at the same time, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations was instructed to organize Ishga Marhamat mono-centers, vocational training centers and short-term vocational training courses by January 1, 2021.

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

One of the most significant steps taken by the Government was the introduction of a system of safe, orderly and legal labor migration, which provides for [8]:

approval of the Action Plan (effective January 1, 2021) to establish compulsory vocational education and foreign language training for citizens traveling abroad for employment, issuance of internationally recognized certificates confirming their professional qualifications to migrants; provision of financial and social support to migrant workers who are in a difficult situation abroad. There are also plans to expand the practice of life and health insurance of migrant workers and ensure the reintegration of persons who have returned from labor migration;

in order to ensure the rapid dissemination of information in the field of external labor migration, the official information channels of the Agency for External Labor Migration were launched online through social networks;

from January 1, 2021, temporary employment abroad through organized labor migration corresponds to the types of activities (works, services) that self-employed persons can engage in. Another initiative based on Article 369 of the Tax Code exempts self-employed persons from income tax – they can (voluntarily) pay a social contribution to the national Pension fund;

migrants who return from abroad and register in the unified database described above are entitled to a subsidy of 2.2 million rubles. sums (about 175 euros) intended to pay for the first three months of renting a commercial space (from the date of registration as an individual entrepreneur);

plans were initiated to launch a call center through an online platform in Russia to provide legal assistance to migrants.

In conclusion, we can say that the recently adopted legislative acts and documents presented in this publication give a powerful impetus to the implementation of the Strategy of Actions in support of employment of citizens outside Uzbekistan, as well as reintegration upon return. These documents should contribute to the implementation of comprehensive measures aimed at increasing the incomes and living standards of families of Uzbek migrant workers by helping to solve the problems they may face – improving housing conditions and ensuring employment of the able-bodied population. Based on the above, the followings are proposed to improve labor migration in Uzbekistan:

First, the Agency for External Labor Migration should create a communication channel with labor migrants to receive feedback (and complaints) about the work performed - or this issue can be included in an existing database. In addition, it is necessary to ensure broad communication with private employment agencies

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

online, through social networks and Telegram channels, as well as provide information about potential foreign employers and the demand for labor;

Second, collecting data from private employment agencies, job seekers, and training providers can help in assessing the existing needs of the labor market abroad. The collected data can contribute to improving the supply of necessary skills and the overall recruitment process (e.g. through targeted job advertisements on relevant online platforms). This data can also improve the assistance provided when signing employment contracts and help clarify the obligations of the parties.

Third, it is necessary to initiate various sociological surveys to monitor the dynamics of economic, political and social indicators related to migration. Surveys could study the factors and causes of labor migration by region; help in determining the directions and forms of migration; assess the working conditions of labor migrants; determine the channels of job search by labor migrants. They can be included in the national information database on labor migration; help in identifying the main factors determining the specific work most often performed by migrants abroad, especially women and youth; help in identifying the main problems and shortcomings faced especially by young people; help in preparing recommendations for regulating labor migration.

Fourth, it is necessary to assess the challenges of the labor market from both the supply and demand side in order to support the growth and productivity of the private sector, expand employment opportunities for workers and fill the skills deficit. Demand-related measures can be mobilized to stimulate economic growth and ensure livelihoods. In terms of the proposal, similar tools should be used in educational development programs.

Fifth, in order to diversify these costs and encourage returning migrants to stay in the country, the Agency for External Labor Migration should more actively conduct trainings in the regions/rural areas on how to start a business and develop business ideas and plans, stimulating the involvement of returning labor migrants in private business and entrepreneurship

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"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

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